

A NOVEL HIGH DENSITY PIEZOELECTRIC SENSING CAPABILITY FOR DETECTION OF IMPACTS IN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a novel acoustic sensing system consisting of a flexible high-density linear piezoelectric sensor array, coupled to a new modular, low-power, low-noise, high-bandwidth data-acquisition platform suitable for aircraft implementation, is presented and applied to in situ modal decomposition of impact acoustic emissions. A carbon-fibre composite panel is subjected to multiple non-damaging impacts at various distances and azimuthal angles of incidence relative to a sensor bonded at the centre of the panel. The acoustic emission (AE) generated by the impacts are localised using this novel system. The challenges in localising AE in a composite panel, the importance of accurate knowledge of material properties, as well as the significance of this new capability for Modal Acoustic Emission (MAE) and Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) of composite materials are discussed.

Keywords: Composites, Acoustic Emission, Lamb Waves, Distributed Sensing, polyvinylidene fluoride sensor

1 INTRODUCTION

The extensive use of composite materials in engineering structures has given rise to significant interest in the development of in-situ Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) systems to monitor the integrity of those structures. The use of composite materials in aircraft primary structure is, relative to metal construction, associated with an increased susceptibility to impact damage from hailstones, runway debris, tool drop and bird strike. These low-velocity impact events can result in Barely Visible Impact Damage (BVID), a type of impact damage which is difficult to detect visually but serious enough to potentially lead to structural failure. The detection of BVID and the impacts that give rise to such damage is of utmost importance.

Various ultrasonic SHM methods have been employed to detect impact damage in composites, including Acoustic Emission (AE) [1], Acousto-Ultrasonics (AU) [2], Electro-Mechanical Impedance (EMI) method [3] and combinations of these methods [4]. A broader review of various non-destructive testing methods for composite materials in [5] identified both AE and AU as prime candidates for rapid global structural health monitoring of composite materials.

The wavefield emanating from an impact in a plate-like structure typically consists of multiple Lamb modes, making analysis of a single-point time-domain signal acquired using a conventional ultrasonic sensor, such as a Piezoelectric Wafer Active Sensor (PWAS [6]), challenging e.g. [7,8]. The single-point sensing traditionally applied in guided wave non-destructive testing e.g. [9], AU e.g. [6] and AE e.g. [10] is quite restrictive. The separation of individual modes in a time record is generally possible at frequencies below the first cut-off, where only three modes exist, providing the distance between the source and sensor is sufficient for separation to occur. However, restricting the frequency bandwidth and modal content of an inspection can limit its diagnostic effectiveness.

Laser Scanning Vibrometry (LSV) has been widely used for grid scanning of guided wave-fields. When combined with a two-dimensional fast Fourier transform (2D-FFT) [11], such scans can be used to produce a frequency-wavenumber decomposition, which allows for the quantification of the contributing modes. Spectral domain filtering can then be used to isolate modes of interest [12,13], and remove boundary reflections [14] and other extraneous components including random noise. After isolating a mode, its time domain contribution can be retrieved via an inverse Fourier transform, as

demonstrated in [15]. This allows for a more judicious selection of mode and frequency bands from which arrival times can be computed for range estimation. However, LSV systems are cumbersome and not suitable for in situ applications. As such, their use is typically restricted to the laboratory. This limitation led to the development of the first in situ modal decomposition capability, which was developed using a high-density multi-element fibre Bragg grating (FBG) array, as reported in [16]. The efficacy of this sensor as a SHM capability was demonstrated experimentally by quantifying Lamb mode conversion at structural inhomogeneities in an aluminium plate.

The sensing array described in [16] is applicable only in circumstances in which the acoustic source can be controlled, a requirement that stems from the need to interrogate each of the sensing elements in the array sequentially. This requirement precludes a straightforward implementation of the capability to the capture and modal decomposition of AE. Because the originating events in AE are spontaneous and isolated, the sensing elements in an array must be interrogated simultaneously.

In this paper, an alternative sensing approach for AE, first introduced in [17], is presented. The novel acoustic sensing system consists of a high density multi-element polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) sensor array coupled to a new modular, low-power, low-noise, high-bandwidth data-acquisition platform suitable for aircraft implementation. The system enables in situ modal decomposition of impact acoustic emissions, thus potentially opening new opportunities in damage classification and quantification based on characteristic modal signatures or fingerprints [15]. The significance of this new capability to Modal Acoustic Emission (MAE) and SHM of composite materials will be discussed.

2 A LINEAR ARRAY FOR MODAL DECOMPOSITION AND ANALYSIS

As previously mentioned, this new capability comprises two key elements, the first of which is a flexible PVDF based multi-element sensor array (Figure 1(a)) which is referred to by the acronym LAMDA, for Linear Array for Modal Decomposition and Analysis. The LAMDA works on the same basic principle established in [16]. The construction of the LAMDA is similar to that of a sensor reported in [18], but with several key differences. The LAMDA is designed to be in a V-shaped sensor array; is smaller in plan-wise dimension and is approximately 20% thinner, as shown in Figure 1(a) and (b). Each arm of the sensor is made up of 16 sensing elements that are rectangular, $\sim 1 \times 5$ mm in size and spaced at a pitch of 1.27 mm leading to an overall footprint on the host (bonded area) of 2 times $\sim 20 \times 5$ mm, dimensionally similar to a large biaxial electrical resistance strain gauge. The V-shaped design evolved from limitations in the first version of LAMDA reported in [17], which will be discussed later in this paper. The sensor has a thickness of ~ 250 μm and an overall mass of 560 mg; however this includes a 50 mm long section of un-bonded track (not shown in Figure 1(a)) so the mass bonded to the structure is less than 250 mg. The small footprint, low mass and high compliance of the thin polymer construction (including flexible printed circuit, or FPC) minimises the inertial and structural impact of the sensor, as will be reported elsewhere. The flexibility ensures excellent conformability, which is an advantage for curved structural surfaces. It also facilitates the use of low-viscosity adhesives, which foster thinner bond lines, thereby minimising shear lag and acoustic attenuation effects.

The second key element of this capability is the instrument pictured in Figure 1(c), which is termed the AUSAM⁺, for Acousto-Ultrasonic for Structural health monitoring Array Module. A comprehensive description of this device was given in [20], so it suffices here to repeat only a few details that are relevant to the present work. The device has four variable-gain piezoelectric send/receive channels, each with a 50 kHz - 5 MHz bandwidth and excellent low noise performance by virtue of its electronic design and EMI hardened packaging. Units can be used in isolation or connected via a synchronous optical link to create a sensing network of up to 248 independent channels. For the present study, a networked configuration consisting of 8 units was used to accommodate the 32 element LAMDA shown in Figure 1(a).

Figure 1: (a) LAMDA; (b) Through-thickness section of LAMDA; (c) AUSAM⁺.

3 THEORY OF OPERATION

A detailed description of the source localisation procedure using LAMDA is given in [17,19] so only a brief outline is provided here. The first step in the procedure is to acquire time signals from the LAMDA, which is done simultaneously across the 32 sensing elements via the AUSAM⁺. Figure 2 depicts schematically the AE from a localised source that is sufficiently distant from the LAMDA that a single mode component of the AE signal can be regarded as a plane wave with wave vector, \mathbf{k} . This plane wave strikes the N element LAMDA at angle θ , relative to the longitudinal axis of one of the sensor arms, the centre of which chosen to be at the origin. Assuming the sensor behaves ideally, i.e. with negligible inertial effect and a sensing area that is negligibly small in comparison to the wavelength, the disturbance sampled by the array has an apparent wavenumber,

$$k_s = k \cos \theta . \quad (1)$$

Applying a 2D-FFT to the set of N simultaneously acquired time vectors, each consisting of M samples, yields a discrete wavenumber spectrum given by

$$H_{k+1,f+1} = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M u_{n,m} e^{-2\pi i(n-1)k/N} e^{-2\pi i(m-1)f/M} \quad (2)$$

Here, k and f are wavenumber and frequency indices respectively and u is the measured signal, which, for a PVDF sensor, is a voltage that is proportional to the strain rate. The wavenumber resolution and Nyquist limit of the array can be determined by sampling theory. These parameters are a function of only two sensor dimensions; the sensor pitch and the array length. For the dimensions given in Figure 1, the relevant calculations yield a resolution and Nyquist limit of 331 rad/m and 2474 rad/m, respectively. A brief description of the range and azimuthal angle estimation is given below, followed by an experimental demonstration on a composite panel subject to non-damaging impact.

Figure 2: Plane wave with wave vector \mathbf{k} and amplitude $A(\mathbf{k})$ striking a linear array of N sensor elements at an azimuthal angle θ .

3.1 Range Estimation

Following the generation of the wavenumber-frequency decomposition, individual time-domain contributions are separated by first isolating the required mode(s) in the frequency range(s) of interest via an appropriately shaped pass-band filter. An inverse Fourier transform is then applied to generate the corresponding time signal. A Hilbert transform is then applied and the arrival-time determined from the peak in the time signal envelope.

Consider the case of two modes; $m1$ and $m2$, propagating at the respective frequencies $f1$ and $f2$. Once, $t_{m,f}^a$, the arrival time for a mode with group velocity, $v_{m,f}^{gr}$, is extracted, the time of impact, t_0 , is obtained from the expression,

$$t_0 = \frac{v_{m1,f1}^{gr} t_{m1,f1}^a - v_{m2,f2}^{gr} t_{m2,f2}^a}{v_{m1,f1}^{gr} - v_{m2,f2}^{gr}}, \quad (3)$$

The distance to the impact, r , relative to the centre of the sensor arm is then calculated using the following expression,

$$r = \frac{v_{m1,f1}^{gr} v_{m2,f2}^{gr} \Delta t_{2,1}^a}{v_{m1,f1}^{gr} - v_{m2,f2}^{gr}} \quad (4)$$

3.2 Azimuthal Angle of Arrival

In cases where the wave-vector is not aligned with the principal axis of either of the sensor arms, the modal signatures produced by the LAMDA will not coincide with the theoretical wavenumber-frequency dispersion curves. This mismatch provides the basis for determining the azimuthal angle of arrival, θ , and can be recovered by rearranging equation (1), viz.

$$\theta = \cos^{-1} \frac{k_s}{k} \quad (5)$$

Here, k_s corresponds to a point along the line of peak energy in the modal signature encompassed in the pass-band filter, and k is a point along the theoretical dispersion curve at the same frequency. Whilst the magnitude of the angle can be determined from equation (5), the sign cannot, which means the source could be in either one of two possible quadrants. This ambiguity is resolved by analyzing the signal from the orthogonal sensor arm, for which case equation (5) always yields an apparent wavenumber of zero, i.e. a featureless wavenumber spectrum when the signal is aligned with the x -direction. Such an arrangement also removes a blind-spot in the single arm design [17,18].

4 EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

An experimental study was conducted on a square fibre composite panel with a side dimension of 560 mm and 2.1 mm thick; manufactured from 16 layers of unidirectional IM7/5250-4 pre-preg in a $[90,-45,45,0,0,45,-45,90]_s$ layup. The mechanical properties of the pre-preg are listed in Table 1 and were used to obtain the dispersion curves for the laminate from Rayleigh-Lamb theory [21] (Figure 3). A LAMDA was attached at the centre of the panel using cyanoacrylate adhesive, such that one of the sensor arms was fixed in alignment with the 0° ply direction. As previously mentioned, eight AUSAM⁺ units were networked to produce a 32-channel system. The system is initially launched in “stand-by” mode, in which it records continuously to a cyclic buffer until a prescribed threshold signal value is exceeded, which signifies the arrival of an AE. The signal record is then sent to a computer for modal decomposition and analysis.

The acoustic source was generated by low-velocity ball-drop impact using a ball-bearing 10 mm in diameter and 4 g in mass. A drop height of 1.2 m was maintained throughout the testing. The ball was held via a magnetic field generated by a solenoid which was de-energised to initiate the drop on the panel, which sat freely on a benchtop with a layer of bubble-wrap in between to acoustically isolate it. The composite panel was impacted at the locations indicated in Figure 4. Initial impacts were applied along the 0° direction, at 50 mm to 200 mm from the origin, in 50 mm increments, to quantify the acoustic damping in the plate. It was found that only the A_0 mode at low frequency was detectable at

ranges greater than 100 mm. Therefore, the panel was subsequently impacted at 14 different locations, evenly spaced along two circular arcs at distances of 50 mm and 100 mm from the origin, as shown in Figure 4. Ten impacts were introduced at each location and the modal signatures were found to be consistent for each impact; however, for brevity, only a few results are reported here.

Table 1: Mechanical properties of IM7/5250-4 pre-preg [22]

Lamina ply	
Elastic modulus (GPa)	
$E_{11} = 162; E_{22} = E_{33} = 9.7; G_{12} = G_{23} = G_{13} = 5.9;$	
Poisson's ratio, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{23} = \nu_{13} = 0.3;$	
Density, $\rho = 1.5 \text{ g/cm}^3$	

Figure 3: Group velocity (left) and wavenumber (right) dispersion curves for the composite panel, obtained from Rayleigh-Lamb theory.

Figure 4: Impact locations relative to LAMDA.

4.1 Impact at $r = 50 \text{ mm}$, $\theta = 0^\circ$

Figure 5(a) shows the signal recorded at sensor element 8 for an impact at a distance of 50 mm from the sensor origin and aligned with the 0° direction. The signal resembles a frequency down-chirp, which is characteristic of the A_0 mode. The time-history recorded by all 32 sensing elements of the array is shown in Figure 5(b). A 2D-FFT was applied to the set of time signals acquired along elements 1 to 16, resulting in the wavenumber spectrum shown in Figure 6. The results show a clear discrepancy between the theoretical predictions and experimental dispersion characteristics at

approximately 300 kHz and above for A_0 and above 600 kHz for S_0 . For this reason, all analyses were performed below those frequencies for the respective modes.

Figure 5: (a) Time signal and; (b) wave-field for an impact aligned with the sensor.

Figure 6: Wavenumber dispersion spectrum corresponding to strain response in Figure 5, versus dispersion curves obtained from Rayleigh-Lamb theory.

The spectrum shown in Figure 6 confirms that the low frequency signal observed in the time signal is the A_0 mode and also reveals higher-frequency S_0 and A_0 signal contributions, which are particularly interesting. These modes are not readily distinguished in the time trace, thus highlighting the robustness and potential of this capability to decipher complex modal signatures. For this impact case, two modes were isolated, $\{A_{0,f=40 \text{ kHz}}, S_{0,f=540 \text{ kHz}}\}$, for the localisation calculations, using appropriate pass-band filters, as described in [14]. The time signals, shown in Figure 7, were obtained from an inverse Fourier transform applied to the wavenumber spectrum after nulling values outside the elliptical pass-band regions marked in red in Figure 6, which correspond to the chosen mode-pair. Next, a Hilbert transform was applied to the time signals and the arrival-time determined from the envelope peak. Substituting these values in equation (4) yielded a range estimate of 51.34 mm. This value is within 3% of the known distance, which is remarkably good in view of the discrepancy between the modal signatures and the theoretical dispersion curves noted earlier.

Figure 7: Time signals corresponding to the pass-bands circled in red in Figure 6.

4.2 Impact at $r = 50 \text{ mm}$, $\theta = 30^\circ$

The oblique incidence in this case results in a downward shift of the modal signatures, as shown in Figure 8(a), especially for the $A_{0,f=300 \text{ kHz}}$ mode and $S_{0,f>550 \text{ kHz}}$. The azimuthal angle was determined first using the pass-band regions outlined in blue in Figure 8(a). A broader pass-bandwidth is used to ensure a precise determination of the azimuthal angle of the incident signals. The estimate from the S_0 data was 14.1° , and from the A_0 data 1.7° , resulting in an average of 7.9° and equates to an error of 73.7% error, which is substantial. The reasons for this error will be discussed later in this paper. The next step was to determine the distance of the impact from the sensor. For the range estimation, the modes were isolated using pass-band regions outlined in red in Figure 8(a), which correspond to the mode-pair $\{A_{0,f=10 \text{ kHz}}, S_{0,f=550 \text{ kHz}}\}$. An inverse Fourier transform was applied to each isolated mode to produce the signal time histories shown in Figure 8(b). The time of arrival of the respective modal contribution was determined and used to compute the range, which was estimated to be 54.90 mm from the sensor origin. This equates to an error of 5.62%; a considerably better estimation compared to the azimuthal angle estimation.

Figure 8: (a) Wavenumber spectrum for an impact at $(50 \text{ mm}, 30^\circ)$; (b) Time signals corresponding to the pass-bands circled in red in the wavenumber spectrum.

4.3 Impact at $r = 100 \text{ mm}$, $\theta = 30^\circ$

As the impact distance was increased, the effect of material damping was clearly observed in the results and are shown in Figure 9, with the signal amplitude nearly halved over a distance of 50 mm,

when compared with the response shown in Figure 8 for the same impact energy. The localisation calculations are omitted for brevity. Using the pass-band regions outlined in blue in Figure 9(a), the azimuthal angle was estimated to be 1.25° for S_0 , and 1.86° for A_0 , giving an average of 1.55° with an error of 95.5%. The mode pair $\{A_{0,f=40 \text{ kHz}}, S_{0,f=540 \text{ kHz}}\}$ was used to determine the range, which was estimated to be 98.97 mm, which equates to an error of 1%.

Figure 9: (a) Wavenumber spectrum for an impact at $(100 \text{ mm}, 30^\circ)$; (b) Time signals corresponding to the pass-bands circled in red in the wavenumber spectrum.

5 DISCUSSION

The localisation methodology described in this paper relies on an accurate knowledge of the material properties of the plate subject. The relevant properties used in the present study were sourced from the material manufacturer [22] and were not verified experimentally. The observed discrepancy between the modal signatures obtained from LAMDA and the theoretical dispersion curves for an aligned impact suggest that these published properties are insufficiently accurate for a determination of the azimuthal angle. A more detailed exploration of this issue was undertaken using LSV.

A separate panel of identical composition and layup was used for this additional study. A PWAS disc element, 1 mm thick and 5 mm diameter, was bonded at the centre of this panel using conductive epoxy. A fixed duration ($20 \mu\text{s}$), Hann-modulated tone-burst voltage was applied to the element to generate Lamb waves. The plate was scanned using LSV at tone-burst centre frequencies of 100 kHz to 1 MHz, in 100 kHz increments. Scans were first made in the 90° ply direction, and then in the 0° ply direction, over a length of 149.5 mm at a sampling interval of 0.12 mm. This sampling arrangement was sufficient to resolve the shortest wavelength, estimated to be 1.7 mm at 1 MHz based on the published material properties [22]. The beam of the LSV was aligned normal to the plate so as to measure the out-of-plane component of the velocity. The resulting wave-field was spectrally decomposed and then plotted against the theoretical dispersion curves for the plate, as shown in Figure 10.

The results in Figure 10 are consistent with those from the $(50\text{mm}, 0^\circ)$ impact case. Specifically, the $A_{0,\text{experimental}}$ and $A_{0,\text{theoretical}}$ signatures diverge as the frequency increases, and the $S_{0,\text{experimental}}$ and $S_{0,\text{theoretical}}$ signatures have different inflection points. Another feature of interest is the directional dependence of the experimentally obtained modal signatures, which is expected for the A_0 mode but not for the S_0 as the layup is quasi-isotropic. The experimental data obtained from this study is currently being used to determine a more accurate set of elastic properties for use in the localisation procedure. The results of this revised analysis will be reported elsewhere.

Figure 10: Experimentally sourced wavenumber dispersion curves for the composite panel versus analytical predictions obtained from published material properties. The results on the left correspond to a scan in the 90° ply direction and those on the right to a scan in the 0° ply direction.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The capacity to decompose a wave-field into its constituent modes using a flexible low-profile sensor has the potential to open new opportunities in damage classification and quantification based on characteristic modal signatures or fingerprints. A new multi-element sensor and complementary hardware capable of achieving this has been presented and its application to the localisation of impact AE demonstrated experimentally on a carbon-fibre composite panel. While the distance to an AE was able to be determined with reasonable accuracy, the azimuthal angle was not. This is surmised to be a result of inaccuracy in the material properties used to calculate the dispersion curves for the laminate.

Future work will focus on obtaining more accurate dispersion curves, which are expected to result in improved azimuthal angle estimates. A study will then be undertaken to determine the influence of directional wave propagation on the accuracy of this localisation procedure. Future studies will also consider damaging impacts with a view to developing an understanding of the modal signatures of different types of composite damage resulting from impact including matrix cracking, fibre breakage, and delamination.

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